

A report on *Psammophilus dorsalis* and *Hemidactylus mabouia* from Tamil Nadu, India

Selvaraj Selvamurugan

Translational Health Science and Technology Institute Building (THSTI), Faridabad-121001.

*Email: selva199420@yahoo.in

Received: 01 July 2022 / Revised: 28 August 2022 / Accepted: 04 September 2022 / Published online: 06 September 2022.

How to cite: Selvamurugan, S. (2022). A report on *Psammophilus dorsalis* and *Hemidactylus mabouia* from Tamil Nadu, India, *Scientific Reports in Life Sciences* 3(2), 1-10. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7055170>

Abstract

Report on a *Psammophilus dorsalis* male and *Hemidactylus mabouia* observed at Tamilnadu, India. *Psammophilus dorsalis* was recorded for the first time outside of its type locality extending its range. In this paper, I present a short note on the presence and status of the *P. dorsalis* from Sivanhill (Siththarmalai), Kangeyam, Thirupur district, Tamilnadu state, India.

Keywords: New record, South Indian rock agama, African house geckos, south India.

Introduction

The body temperature of reptiles greatly influences their ability to perform various activities such as digestion, growth, movement, oxygen consumption, reproduction, foraging, escape from a predator, and social interaction (Kearney, 2001). It is widely known that reptiles derive their body heat from external sources and pregnant females actively select the required body temperature rather than passively accepting the available temperature (Mathies & Andrews, 1997). The behavioral mechanisms generally involve shuttling between sun and shade, retreating into deep shade or crevices, basking for variable durations, modifying postures to alter surface areas to be exposed to heat, and altering their activity with respect to environmental temperature (Castilla & Bouwens, 1991; Díaz, 1994; Labra et al., 2001; Radderet al., 2005).

The Peninsular Rock Agama (*Psammophilus dorsalis*) is a common rock-dwelling lizard with a widespread distribution throughout the Indian peninsula at elevations up to 1829 m (Daniel, 2002).

This species is characterized by a large head that is laterally elongated and dorsoventrally depressed. The cheeks are swollen only in adult males and their snout is longer than their orbit. This species shows distinct sexual dimorphism, with males being larger than females. Males are brightly colored only during the breeding season while females show cryptic coloration and often resemble the color of the rocks on which they are found (Smith, 1935).

The Peninsular rock agama *P. dorsalis* (Gray, 1831) occurs in most of Peninsular India, Madhya Pradesh, and along the hills of the Eastern Ghats (Smith, 1935; Daniel, 2002; Chandra & Gajbe, 2005). Its food was considered to consist almost entirely of insects (Daniel, 2002; Radder *et al.*, 2005). There have been no records of *P. dorsalis* in this region. The genus *Hemidactylus* is represented by 49 species in India, accounting for about 27% of the global diversity within the genus (Das *et al.*, 2022; Uetz *et al.*, 2021). Several new species have been described as an outcome of the dedicated explorations and reassessment of species complexes through an integrated approach (Agarwal *et al.*, 2019; Mirza *et al.*, 2018).

Among the most species-rich clade of *Hemidactylus* in India are members of the Prashad group, with 21 described species that mostly comprise large-bodied geckos (Agarwal *et al.*, 2019; Das *et al.* 2022; Lajmi *et al.* 2019). Many species that belong to this group were considered conspecific with *Hemidactylus maculatus* Duméril & Bibron (1836). However, with the aid of molecular data in conjunction with morphological data, several new species have been described in the recent past (Agarwal *et al.* 2019; Chaitanya *et al.* 2018; Das *et al.* 2022; Giriet *et al.* 2017; Khandekar *et al.* 2021; Mirza *et al.* 2017; Mirza and Sanap 2014; Srikanthan *et al.*, 2018). Here, the survey was recorded in *Hemidactylus mabouia* (Moreau de Jonnès, 1818), species in Uthankudi Madurai, and *Psammophilus dorsalis* Sivan hills (Siththar malai) in Kangeyam, Thirupur district, Tamilnadu, India.

Results and discussion

Site 1

Figure 1. Shows that the Peninsular rock agama (*Psammophilus dorsalis*) male in this reptile species recorded from near Sivan hills (Siththarmalai), Kangeyam taluk, Tirupur district, Tamilnadu state, India. *P. dorsalis* is a common agamid across peninsular India and there are numerous studies largely on the behavioral ecology of this Head large, elongated and depressed, cheeks swollen in adult males, body depressed, regularly arranged, 115 to 150 scales around midbody, no proper dorsal crest, only a denticulate ridge, a deep fold on either side of the neck in

front of the shoulder connected across the throat by a transverse fold; no gular sac, tail long and slender, tympanum distinct. No prenatal or femoral pores.

Site 2

Figure 2. *Hemidactylus mabouia* (Moreau de Jonnès, 1818), species recorded in Uthankudi in Madurai district, Tamilnadu state, India. This sub-tropical species originated from Africa and Madagascar and is found on islands of the Mozambique Channel (Murphy, 1997). It is commonly found in environments such as on the bark of trees, and in human habitations like wooden picnic tables, household walls, fences, or near insect-attracting lights (Censky et al., 2003).

Figure 1. Shows species of Indian rock agama found in Siththar hills of Tirupur district Tamilnadu. India *P. dorsalis* is well suited to arid conditions. It was found that these Lizards remain active throughout the day except for the hottest hours. They feed on insects. Fruits etc., the Lizards Siththar hills areas, where enough food supports population. Here the total yearly rainfall is moderate.

2. *Hemidactylus mabouia* (Moreau de Jonnès, 1818)

Figure 2. The study area of *Hemidactylus mabouia* in Uthankudi, Madurai, district Tamilnadu state, India

Characteristics: A small species with a depressed body, developed limbs, and a sturdy tail. Its length ranges from 2cm to 14cm. Its back is grayish or brown, and it may have darker transverse stripes. They have large lidless eyes and dilated fingers, which allow them to climb on smooth walls. They also have a protractile tongue and can easily change their color depending on the color of the substrate.

Distribution: The species occurs in South America, Africa, Madagascar, the Caribbean, and Mexico. In Brazil, it occurs in all regions.

Habitat: Open to forest formations. Always associated with Human environments and commonly found in cracks in houses, under trees bark, fallen logs, and building materials.

Habits: Crepuscular and nocturnal, easily observed near light sources. These animals spend much of their time sitting still, lying waiting for their prey, and may approach them slowly, capturing them with a quick bite.

Diet: Insects and small arthropods.

Breeding: Oviparous, and reproduces year-round. Hatchlings are born measuring about 2cm in length and reach sexual maturity when nearing 5.5cm.

UFRA: The species was spotted in the wild only in Exotic Woods and Wetlands with Herbaceous Plants.

The Indian rock agama is an agamid Lizard associated with rocky terrain in hilly areas of south India (Das 2002, Daniel 2002). It is a sexually dimorphic species, where males are large with black breeding color on the head and lateral sides of the body, and females are smaller than males. Perch height also differs between the sexes. Males prefer to perch at a greater height than females.

In certain agamid Lizards that live in arid regions, the water uptake is by means of transporting water across the skin (Sherbrooke, 1993, Withers, 1993). Further studies are therefore needed to determine if the behavior of *P. dorsalis* involves water uptake rather than thermoregulation as indicated (Veeranagouda et al., 2010). There have been no records of *P. dorsalis* feeding on other smaller Lizards in the past. Agama is insectivorous and also consumes vegetation such as flowers, grasses, and fruits. Their diet consists of mainly ants, grasshoppers, beetles, and termites. *P. dorsalis* is a common agamid across peninsular India and there are numerous studies largely on the behavioral ecology of this species.

Recorded one specimen of reptile species surveyed in this region is identified as *Psammophilus dorsalis*, which is known as Peninsular rock agama female gecko. October 2019, at the Mahalingam Hills from Thirunelveli, Tami Nadu (Selvamurugan et al., 2019). In this record of gecko's south Indian rock agama male *Psammophilus dorsalis* at siththar hills, Thirupur district, Tamilnadu state, India (Torres et al. 2018). The new report is the first record for the invasive species *H. mabouia* in the dry Chaco, a biogeography region included in the Gran Chaco Sudamericano (Naumann, 2006). The presence of *H. mabouia* in this region, which is characterized by the presence of multiple endemism (Szumik et al., 2012), represents a potential problem for the conservation of fauna. As was previously mentioned, some Hemidactylus species share the ability to displace native fauna (Hanley et al., 1998, Dame & Petren, 2006, Rivas Fuenmayor et al., 2005), which suggests the need to carry out a greater survey of the fauna present in the dry Chaco and the potential threats to the conservation of the native fauna. This record extends the distribution range of *H. mabouia* by nearly 300 kilometers (in a straight line) from Formosa city, the nearest point previously reported (Alvarez et al., 2009). Here, spotted in African house gecko (*Hemidactylus mabouia*, Moreau de Jonnès, 1818), species in uthankudi Madurai. Tamilnadu state, india. *Hemidactylus mabouia* is known to have a generalist feeding habit (Vitt, 1995; Zamprogno & Teixeira, 1998), which is also the conclusion of this diet analysis. The animals mainly feed on arthropods, mostly insects.

There have been no records of *P. dorsalis* feeding on other smaller lizards in the past. However, this might be likely as skinks were found in the diet of its sister species *Psammophilus blanfordanus* (Aruna et al., 1993) which is smaller in length when compared. There could be an inter-sexual dietary divergence in this species of agamid due to clear sexual size dimorphisms (Smith, 1935; Radder et al., 2006). Further detailed studies are needed to prove this supposition. It is possible that in nature, lizards use diverse strategies to overcome extreme changes in the ambient temperature that might not be often noticed by an observer. Extensive field studies are needed to reveal mechanisms of thermoregulation, especially in gravid female rock lizards that are exposed to very high temperatures, ordinarily not congenial for the survival of oviductal embryos. There are important implications for the management of invasive species an accurate assessment of diversity within taxa is of critical importance. *Hemidactylus* is a useful model system to understand the evolutionary origins of invasiveness, including many invasive to non-invasive species with restricted distributions. However, basic natural history or descriptive ecological studies on the habitat quality/suitability, diet composition, effects of anthropogenic disturbance, and habitat modification on this species have not been undertaken.

Reference

- Agarwal, I., A.M. Bauer, V.B. Giri & A. Khandekar (2019). An expanded ND2 phylogeny of the Brookii and Prashadi groups with the description of three new Indian *Hemidactylus* Oken (Squamata: Gekkonidae). *Zootaxa* 4619: 431–458. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4619.3.2>.
- Aruna, C.H., Reddy, T.B., Rao, M.V.S. (1993). Feeding ecology of *Psammophilus blanfordanus* (Stoliczka). *J. Bombay Nat. Hist. Soc.* 90(2), 295-296.
- Alvarez, B.B., Ruiz, García A., Céspedes, J.A., Hernando, A., Zaracho, V., Calamante, C., Aguirre, R. (2009). Herpetofauna, provinces of Chaco and Formosa, Chaco Oriental region, north-eastern Argentina. *Check List* 5 (1), 074–082. <http://doi.org/10.15560/5.1.74>
- Chaitanya, R., A. Lajmi & V.B. Giri (2018). A new cryptic, rupicolous species of *Hemidactylus* Oken, 1817 (Squamata: Gekkonidae) from Meghamalai, Tamil Nadu, India. *Zootaxa* 4374: 49–70. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4374.1.3>.
- Chandra, K., Gajbe, P.U. (2005). An inventory of herpetofauna of Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh. *Zoos' Print Journal* 20(3), 1812-1819.
- Censky, Ellen J., Karim V.D., (2003). "The Reptiles and Amphibians of Anguilla British West Indies: Species Accounts – Lizards". Anguilla National Trust.
- Castilla, A.M., Bauwens, D. (1991). Thermal biology, microhabitat selection, and conservation of the insular lizard *Podarcis hispanica atrata*. *Oecologia* 85: 366-374.
- Das, I. (2002). *Snakes and other Reptiles of India*. New Holland, London, UK.

- Daniel, J.C. (2002). The Book of Indian Reptiles and Amphibians. Oxford University Press, Mumbai, India.
- Duméril, A.M.C. & Bibron G. (1836). Érpétologie Générale, ou Histoire Naturelle Complète des Reptiles. Paris: Libraire Encyclopedique deRoret. 518 p.
- Díaz, J.A. (1994): Field thermoregulatory behavior in the western Canarian lizard *Gallotiagalloti*. J. Herpetol. 28: 325-333.
- Dame EA, Petren K (2006) Behavioural mechanisms of invasion and displacement in Pacific island geckos (*Hemidactylus*). Animal Behaviour 71: 1165–1173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2005.10.009>
- Giri, V.B., Bauer, A.M., Mohapatra, P.P., Srinivasulu, C. & Agarwal, I. (2017). A new species of large-bodied, tuberculate *Hemidactylus* Oken (Squamata: Gekkonidae) from the Eastern Ghats, India. Zootaxa 4347(2), 331–345. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4347.2.8>.
- Hanley, K.A., Petren, K., Case, T.J. (1998). An experimental investigation of the competitive displacement of a native gecko by an invading gecko: no role for parasites. Oecologia, 115: 196–205. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s004420050508>.
- Kearney, M. (2001). Postural thermoregulatory behavior in the nocturnal lizards *Christinusmarmoratus* and *Nephurusmilii* (Gekkonidae). Herpetological Review, 32: 11-14.
- Khandekar, A., Thackeray, T. & Agarwal, I. (2021). A cryptic new species of *Hemidactylus rupicolous* Goldfuss, 1820 (Squamata: Gekkonidae) allied to *H. aaronbaueri* Giri, 2008 from the northern Western Ghats of Maharashtra, India. Zootaxa 5020(3): 434–456. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5020.3.2>.
- Labra, A., Soto-Gamboa, M., Bozinovic, F. (2001). Behavioral and physiological thermoregulation of Atacama Desert-dwelling *Liolaemus* lizards. Ecoscience 8, 413-420.
- Uetz, P., Freed, P., Aguilar, R. & Hošek, J. (Eds) (2021). The Reptile Database, <http://www.reptile-database.org>. Accessed on October 25, 2021
- Murphy, J.C. (1997). “Amphibians and Reptiles of Trinidad and Tobago. Kreiger Publishing Company: Part4-Reptilia Species Accounts” Kreiger Drive, Malabar, Florida.
- Mirza, Z.A., Gowande, G., Patil, R., Ambekar, M. & Patel, H. (2018). First appearance deceives many: disentangling the *Hemidactylus triedrus* species complex using an integrated approach. PeerJ, 6: e5341. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.5341>.
- Mirza, Z.A. & Raju, D. (2017). A new rupicolous species of gecko of the genus *Hemidactylus* Oken, 1817 from the Satpura Hills, central India. Amphibian & Reptile Conservation 11: 51–71.
- Mirza, Z.A. & Sanap, R.V. (2014). A new cryptic species of gecko of the genus *Hemidactylus* Oken, 1817 (Reptilia: Gekkonidae) from Southern India. Taprobanica 6, 12–20. <http://doi.org/10.4038/tapro.v6i1.7056>.
- Mathies.T, Andrews, R.M. (1997). Influence of pregnancy on the thermal biology of the lizard *Sceloporus jarrovi*: why do pregnant females exhibit low body temperatures? Functional Ecology, 11 (1997), pp. 498-507.

- Radder, R.S., Saidapur, S.K., Shanbhag, B.A. (2005). Population density, microhabitat use and activity pattern of the Indian rock lizard, *Psammophilus dorsalis*. *Current Science* 89: 560-565.
- Rivas, Fuenmayor, G., Ungueto, G.N., Bauer, A.M., Barros, T., Manzanilla, J. (2005). Expansion and natural history of a successful colonizing gecko in Venezuela (Reptilia: Gekkonidae: *Hemidactylus mabouia*) and the discovery of *H. frenatus* in Venezuela. *Herpetological Review* 36 (2). 121–125.
- Smith, M.A. (1935). The Fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Reptilia and Amphibia. Sauria, Taylor and Francis, London. 2, 209-210pp.
- Sherbrooke, W.C. (1993). Rain-drinking behaviors of the Australian thorny devil (Sauria: Agamidae), *Journal of Herpetology*, 27, 270–275.
- Szumik, C., Aagesen, L., Casagrande, D., Arzamendia, V., Baldo, D., Claps, L.E., Cuzzo, F., Díaz, Gómez, J.M., Di Giacomo, A., Giraud, A., Goloboff, P., Gramajo, C., Kopuchian, C., Kretzschmar, S., Lizarralde, M., Molina, A., Mollerach, M., Navarro, F., Nomdedeu, S., Panizza, A., Pereyra, V.V., Sandoval, M., Scrocchi, G., Zuloaga, F.O. (2012). Detecting areas of endemism with a taxonomically diverse data set: plants, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, birds, and insects from Argentina. *Cladistics* 28 (3), 317–329. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-0031.2011.00385.x>.
- Srikanthan, A.N., Swamy, P., Mohan, A.V. & Pal. S. (2018). A distinct new species of riparian rock-dwelling gecko (genus: *Hemidactylus*) from the southern Western Ghats, *Zootaxa* 4434: 141–157, <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4434.1.9>.
- Torres, P.J., Escalante, O., Cardozo, D. (2018). First record of the invasive *Hemidactylus mabouia* (Moreau de Jonnès, 1818) (Squamata, Gekkonidae), in the dry Chaco, Argentina. *Check List* 14 (4), 633–636. <https://doi.org/10.15560/14.4.633>.
- Uetz, P., P. Freed, R. Aguilar & J. Hošek (Eds) (2021). The Reptile Database, <http://www.reptile-database.org>. Accessed on October 25, 2021.
- Vitt, L.J. 1995. The Ecology of Tropical Lizards in the Caatinga of Northeast of Brazil. *Occ. Pap. Oklahoma Mus. Natural History*, 1, 1-29.
- Veeranagoudar, D.K., Shanbhag, B.A., Saidapur, S.K. (2010). A novel thermoregulatory behaviour in gravid rock lizard, *Psammophilus dorsalis*. *Herpetology Notes*, 3, 101-103.
- Withers, P. (1993). Cutaneous water acquisition by the thorny devil (*Moloch horridus*; Agamidae). *Journal of Herpetology* 27, 265–270.
- Zamprogno, C., TEIXEIRA, R.L., *Hábitos alimentares* da lagartixa-de-parede *Hemidactylus mabouia* (Reptilia, Gekkonidae) da planície litorânea do norte do Espírito Santo, Brasil. *Revista Brasileira de Biologia*, 1998, 58, 143-50.